

DESIGNING A SMART PEDESTRIAN CROSSING

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Abstrakt: The indicator of environmental safety of road users depends on the exposure of urban residents to pollutants emitted by motor vehicles. Based on this indicator, the quality of the ambient air for pedestrians, passengers and drivers of public and private transport is evaluated. Taking into account the changes in the level of use of cars, as well as the reduction of pollutant emissions from the movement of vehicles, it is necessary to pay attention to the cleaning properties of trees around the roads, the concentration of carbon and nitrogen oxides. The quality of the traffic flow is characterized by the level of comfort, level of service, smooth movement, ease of driving, etc. operating costs. All these indicators are interrelated: for example, the speed when the intensity of movement changes, 548 Science and innovation international scientific journal volume 1 ISSUE 8 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 safety and ease of movement, freedom of maneuverability, etc. will change. The intensity and speed of traffic have a significant impact on operational costs, ease of movement, safety of movement, and time spent on the trip .

Keywords: Smart pedestrians, smart intersections, parking spaces, sensors.

Introduction: Pedestrians cross the road an average of two to three times during their journey, and may also need to cross railways, waterways or other natural features. One of our main tasks is to ensure ease of movement and safety when crossing roads. Therefore, the proper design, construction, and reconstruction of appropriate crossings should be a major consideration in the development of pedestrian routes[1]. In our country, road traffic accidents are happening very quickly, including in 2019, in 8,092 road traffic accidents, a total of 9,990 people were injured, of which 2,067 people died (death indicator is 20.7%), in 2020, 8 thousand 553 citizens were injured in 6 982 road traffic accidents and 1 thousand 962 people died (death rate is 23%). In 2021, 9 thousand 230 citizens were injured and 2 thousand 436 people died in 10 001 traffic accidents (mortality rate 21%). As a result of 7,636 traffic accidents that occurred in January-October 2022, 1,931 people died, 226 of them were children.

The main causes of pedestrian collisions are[2]:

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- often caused by drivers not following traffic rules;
- unsatisfactory condition of the pedestrian crossing and its equipment. It has been proven that every sixth traffic accident involving a pedestrian at a pedestrian crossing occurs for this very reason[3];
- the psychophysiological factors of the pedestrian, for example, the natural desire to save time by choosing the shortest path, thereby violating traffic rules, the physiological characteristics of pedestrians, and therefore their quick and accurate perception in order to deploy the technical means of organizing pedestrian traffic all structures should be designed taking into account[4];
- weather conditions: rain, mud, fog, etc.; large vehicles blocking the pedestrian crossing sign; the unsatisfactory state of vehicles, especially during the spring-autumn thaw. To ensure safety, a sighting device called a sighting triangle is required (Figure 1). Often, when it is built, there are conflicting requirements for convenience.

Pedestrian crossings are classified according to the way pedestrians cross the carriageway[5]:

- Pedestrian crossings of different levels with the carriageway; Pedestrian crossings on the carriageway (on the ground). Crossings with the carriageway of the pedestrian crossing at different levels are divided into the following depending on the level of traffic and pedestrian visibility[6]:

- crossing the pedestrian crossing;
- passing under the pedestrian crossing;

Methods: Smart Crosswalks are essential for safer and more efficient roads in expanding urban areas with high traffic volume. Cutting-edge technology and innovative systems must be integrated to protect pedestrians[7].

Figure-1. Smart crosswalk.

Imagine a bustling city street during rush hour. Pedestrians are crossing the road, cars are zooming by, and the chaos of urban life is in full swing. During this organized chaos, Smart Crosswalks silently work to ensure the safety of those on foot. The sensors embedded in these crosswalks are capable of detecting even the slightest movement, allowing them to track the presence of pedestrians and vehicles. This real-time data is then sent to traffic management systems, where it is analyzed and used to make informed decisions[8]. The data collected by Smart Crosswalks can be utilized to identify patterns and trends in pedestrian and vehicle behavior. This valuable information can then be used to make data-driven traffic management and infrastructure development decisions. For example, if a particular crosswalk consistently experiences heavy foot traffic during certain hours, city planners can use this data to justify the installation of additional crosswalks or the implementation of traffic calming measures in the area. Omniflow Smart Crosswalks are a

game-changer when it comes to pedestrian safety and traffic efficiency. With their ability to detect movement, provide real-time data, and optimize visual alerts, these intelligent systems ensure the well-being of pedestrians while improving the overall traffic flow[9]. As cities continue to grow and evolve, the implementation of Smart Crosswalks will undoubtedly play a vital role in creating safer and more efficient transportation networks for all[10].

Warning Module:

The warning module includes the following two parts: a voice alert pile and an intelligent crosswalk. The voice alert pile can be adopted from the existing intersection voice alert pile. The control program of the existing intersection voice alert pile can be re-modified and connected to the system. If there is no voice alert pile at the intersection, additional voice alert piles can be set up[11].

Rista et al studied the impact of signs on driver yield situation and showed that LED embedded signs are an effective treatment

solution at the sidewalk, and that they lower operating speeds. As a result, the choice of LED lights for the smart crosswalk light-emitting component was considered, and the smart crosswalk was installed in place of the traditional crosswalk. Considering that in engineering

applications, LED lights need to have high brightness, easy identification, long life, low energy consumption, etc. So, the ND16 series LED high brightness indicator is selected in this paper, and the effect is shown in Figure 7[12].

Figure-7. ND16 series light-emitting diode high brightness indicator effect.

Results: When traffic is heavy, equipped, unregulated or regulated pedestrian crossings are held. Pedestrian crossing is marked by line 1.14- "zebra", 1.12 "stop line" where vehicles stop. The stop line should not be more than 1 meter from the edge of the pedestrian crossing. In addition to the signs 5.16.1 (left) and 5.16.2 (right), a 1.20 "Pedestrian Crossing" warning sign shall be placed 50 and 150 m away from the crossing to mark the pedestrian crossing outside the settlements. If there is no demarcation line on the carriageway, on the opposite side of the road, at a distance of 1 m from the border of the crossing, signs 5.16 indicate the width of the crossing. When the speed of pedestrians is 200 people / hour, the speed of vehicles approaching the crossing will be limited. To do this, on both sides of the crosswalk, between 100 and 150 m, a 3.24 "Maximum speed limit" sign will be placed, resulting in a reduction in speed of at least 20 km / h[13].

Conclusion: Smartpass leverages technology into pedestrian traffic safety improvement. The system consists of several modules that can be added to the pedestrian crossing depending on the location. It uses a passive infrared system to detect approaching person and activate warning lights on top of the sign as well as those along the passage. It can also be equipped with a radar measuring the velocity of approaching vehicles, sound warning system and a camera monitoring the crossing in real time. Each year there are approximately 4 000 accidents on pedestrian crossings in Poland alone that cause 260 fatalities. Smartpass is an enhanced system of active pedestrian crossings previously known as APP Zebra that have been installed in over 150 places in Poland. With its upgraded version, the company is ready to deploy its systems worldwide. The study made by Warsaw Polytechnic states that developed system increases pedestrian's safety by up to 25%.

REFERENCES

1. Alijon o'g'li, E. O., & Sodiq o'g'li, M. U. (2024). Uarm robots in python data base formation electrical principle and structure scheme design. *European Journal of Emerging Technology and Discoveries*, 2(2), 43-47.
URL:<https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/42>
2. Alijon o'g'li, E. O. (2023). Robototexnik tizmlarning tashqi ob'ektlarga ta'sir ko'rsatishida gidroyuritmalardan foydalanish usullari. *Mexatronika va robototexnika: muammolar va rivojlantirish istiqbollari*, 1(1), 102-104.
URL:<https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/43>
3. Ergashev, O. A. O. G. L. (2022). Robototexnik tizimlarning tashqi obyektlarga ta'sir ko'rsatishida suyuqlik oqimlaridan foydalanish usullarini tadqiq etish. *Science and Education*, 3(6), 399-402.

4. Alijon o'g'li, Ergashev Odiljon, va Qo'ldashboev Raxmatullox Zafarbek o'g'li. "quyos paneli monitoring mexatron moduli loyihalanih". *Rivojlanayotgan texnologiyalar va kashfiyotlar Yevropa jurnali* 2.4 (2024): 68-77.
5. Alijon o'g'li, Ergashev Odiljon, va Juraev Asilbek Xotamjon o'g'li. "Zamonaviy scada tizimida isiliklarni loyihalashtirish". *Rivojlanayotgan texnologiyalar va kashfiyotlar Yevropa jurnali* 2.4 (2024): 36-43.
6. Xolmatov Oybek Olim o'g'li, & Xoliqov Izzatulla Abdumalik o'g'li. (2023). Quyosh paneli yuzasini tozalovchi mobile roboti taxlili. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(7), 791–800.
URL: <https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/424>
7. Xolmatov Oybek Olim o'g'li, & Vorisov Raxmatulloh Zafarjon o'g'li. (2023). Kalava ipi ishlab chiqarishda paxtani sifatini nazorat qilish muammolarining taxlili. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(7), 801–810.
URL: <https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/425>
8. Холматов Ойбек Олим угли, & Иминов Холмуродбек Элмуродбек угли. (2023). Экстракция хлопкового масла с использованием технологии субкритической воды. экстракция хлопкового масла с использованием технологии субкритической воды. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(7), 852–860.
URL: <https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/432>
9. Холматов Ойбек Олим угли, & Хасанов Жамолитдин Фазлитдин угли. (2023). Автоматическая система очистки солнечных панелей на базе arduino для удаления пыли. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(7), 861–871.
URL: <https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/433>
10. Xolmatov Oybek Olim o'g'li, & Jo'rayev Zoxidjon Azimjon o'g'li. (2023). Machine learning yordamida idishni sathini aniqlash. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(7), 1163–1170.
URL: <https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/477>
11. Холматов О.О., Муталипов Ф.У. "Создание пожарного мини-автомобиля на платформе Arduino" *Universum: технические науки : электрон. научн. журн.* 2021. 2(83).
URL: <https://7universum.com/ru/tech/archive/item/11307>
11. Холматов О.О., Дарвишев А.Б. "Автоматизация умного дома на основе различных датчиков и Arduino в качестве главного контроллера" *Universum: технические науки : электрон. научн. журн.* 2020. 12(81).
URL: <https://7universum.com/ru/tech/archive/item/11068>
DOI:10.32743/UniTech.2020.81.12-1.25-28
12. Холматов О.О., Бурхонов З.А. "проекты инновационных парковок для автомобилей" *Международный научный журнал «Вестник науки» № 12 (21) Том 4 ДЕКАБРЬ 2019 г.*
URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=41526101>
13. Kholmatov O.O., Burkhonov Z., Akramova G. "The search for optimal conditions for machining composite materials" *science and world International scientific journal*, №1(77), 2020, Vol.I
URL: http://en.scienceph.ru/f/science_and_world_no_1_77_january_vol_i.pdf#page=28
14. Холматов О.О., Бурхонов З, Акрамова Г "автоматизация и управление промышленными роботами на платформе arduino" *science and education scientific journal volume #1 ISSUE #2 MAY 2020*
URL: <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/389>
15. Кабулов Н. А., Холматов О.О "AUTOMATION PROCESSING OF HYDROTHERMIC PROCESSES FOR GRAINS" *Universum: технические науки журнал декабрь 2021 Выпуск: 12(93) DOI - 10.32743/UniTech.2021.93.12.12841*
URL: <https://7universum.com/ru/tech/archive/item/12841>
DOI - 10.32743/UniTech.2021.93.12.12841